

CRM-GEOTHERMAL DELIVERABLE D6.5

EDUCATIONAL PLAN

Summary:

This deliverable outlines how CRM-geothermal results can be exploited through education at secondary school and university levels. It assesses current practices, identifies gaps, and proposes recommendations for curricula, teaching methods, and partnerships, with a focus on geothermal energy and critical raw materials.

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable has been developed within Task 6.5 *Ensure exploitation of project results* of the CRM-geothermal project. Its objective is to complement the project's exploitation strategy by providing guidance for integrating geothermal energy and critical raw materials (CRM) into education at both secondary school and university levels. By strengthening geoscience education, this Educational Plan aims to increase awareness among young people, inspire future professionals, and secure a skilled workforce able to advance Europe's twin transition under the Green Deal.

The report first assesses the status of geoscience education in European secondary schools. Although Earth sciences are critical for understanding resource management, climate change, and sustainable energy, they are often marginalised in curricula and taught by non-specialist teachers. Student interest is high when topics connect to real-world challenges such as natural hazards or sustainability, but limited teaching resources and training opportunities remain key barriers.

The CRM-geothermal video contest, organised for students aged 12–18, demonstrated that interactive formats can effectively raise interest in geoscience. Participation patterns showed stronger engagement among older teenagers and female students, while social media dissemination highlighted the need for tailored outreach strategies. Lessons from the contest provide useful directions for future engagement activities in schools.

Based on these assessments, the plan formulates recommendations for secondary schools: to integrate geoscience more explicitly into curricula, promote inquiry-based and experiential learning (fieldwork, virtual field trips, gamification), provide targeted teacher training, and develop ready-to-use materials linked to energy transition and raw materials.

At the university level, a review of European programmes reveals strong foundations in geology, mining, and environmental engineering, but limited integration of geothermal-CRM co-production concepts. The plan therefore recommends updating curricula to include new modules on sustainable raw materials derived from geothermal fluids, ESG (environmental, social, and governance) principles, and social licence to operate, as well as digital tools such as the CRM Fluid Atlas, and interdisciplinary programmes linking geoscience, engineering, policy, and economics. A roadmap is proposed for gradual implementation, from short-term elective courses to long-term dedicated degree programmes.

In conclusion, this Educational Plan supports the CRM-geothermal exploitation strategy by bridging research, education, and skills development. By equipping secondary school students with awareness and university students with specialised knowledge, the project contributes to building a new generation of professionals able to deliver sustainable supplies of raw materials and renewable energy for Europe's future.

2 INTRODUCTION

Education is a cornerstone for ensuring the long-term impact and exploitation of CRM-geothermal project results. By integrating knowledge of geothermal energy and critical raw materials (CRMs) into school and university curricula, the project can inspire future generations, foster societal awareness, and prepare a skilled workforce capable of delivering sustainable resource management and energy solutions. This Educational Plan therefore complements the project's exploitation strategy by identifying current gaps in geoscience education, analysing engagement outcomes from the video contest, and providing recommendations for both secondary schools and universities.

The plan has three overarching goals:

- To strengthen the visibility of geoscience in education, with particular emphasis on geothermal energy and CRM supply.
- To translate CRM-geothermal project results into practical tools and recommendations for teachers and educators.
- To support Europe's strategic objectives under the Green Deal¹, Critical Raw Materials Act², and Sustainable Development Goals³ by preparing the next generation of professionals.

In line with Task 6.5 *Ensure exploitation of project results*, the plan addresses both the public education sector and higher education institutions. It builds on surveys and international studies on geoscience education, lessons learned from the CRM-geothermal video contest, and mapping of relevant university programmes in Europe.

2.1 BACKGROUND

The European Green Deal, the digital transition, and the energy transition depend on secure and sustainable access to critical raw materials. At the same time, public resistance to new mining projects in Europe highlights the importance of alternative and socially acceptable approaches to raw material supply. CRM-geothermal proposes the combined production of renewable geothermal energy and CRMs from subsurface fluids, thereby minimising land use, environmental impact, and societal opposition.

To ensure the uptake and long-term sustainability of this innovative approach, education plays a decisive role. Awareness at the secondary school level supports early interest in geosciences, resource awareness, and climate action, while updated university curricula ensure that students are educated in the interdisciplinary skills needed for future CRM-geothermal developments. Embedding project results in education therefore contributes directly to the exploitation strategy by:

- Building societal trust and acceptance for geothermal-CRM projects.
- Expanding the talent pipeline for industry, academia, and policy.
- Ensuring knowledge transfer from research into practice and policy.
- Positioning Europe as a global leader in sustainable raw materials and geothermal technologies.

¹ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

² https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/sectors/raw-materials/areas-specific-interest/critical-raw-materials/critical-raw-materials-act_en

³ <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>

2.2 OBJECTIVES AND SCOPE

The overarching purpose of this Educational Plan is to ensure that the results of the CRM-geothermal project are effectively exploited through education, reaching both young learners in secondary schools and students at university level. Education is a critical enabler for long-term impact: it raises awareness of the importance of geothermal energy and critical raw materials, inspires future professionals, and ensures that Europe has the skilled workforce needed for the twin green and digital transitions.

More specifically, the plan has five interlinked objectives that define its scope. The first is to assess the status of geoscience education in European secondary schools, with an emphasis on how topics related to geothermal energy and raw materials are currently integrated into curricula. This assessment draws on recent surveys and studies conducted by organisations such as EFG, IGEO, UNESCO, and the ENGIE project, as well as examples of good practice from across Europe.

The second objective is to evaluate the results of the CRM-geothermal video contest. By analysing participation rates, demographic profiles, and dissemination outcomes, the report identifies which approaches are most effective in sparking student interest and engagement. The insights from this case study provide concrete lessons for future outreach activities.

Building on these findings, the plan aims thirdly to formulate recommendations for secondary schools. These recommendations are intended to support teachers and education policymakers by offering practical guidance on how to bring geoscience, sustainability, and raw materials into the classroom. Suggestions include integrating geothermal and CRM content into science subjects, using experiential and inquiry-based teaching methods, and developing accessible learning resources.

At the higher education level, the plan's fourth objective is to map and evaluate existing university programmes in geology, mining, raw materials, and geothermal energy. This overview highlights both existing strengths and current gaps, particularly the limited presence of interdisciplinary approaches that combine renewable energy production with raw material recovery.

Finally, the plan seeks to provide recommendations for universities to update their curricula. This includes the introduction of new modules on geothermal-CRM co-production, sustainability and ESG (environmental, social, governance) frameworks, geoethics, and digital tools such as the CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas. A phased roadmap is proposed: short-term elective modules, medium-term joint Master's programmes, and long-term interdisciplinary degrees that fully align with Europe's policy priorities, including the Green Deal, the Critical Raw Materials Act, and the Sustainable Development Goals.

To summarise, the scope of this report is broad yet focused. It covers both secondary and tertiary education, combines assessment with practical recommendations, and connects teaching with the strategic needs of Europe's future energy and raw material systems. Its ultimate goal is to ensure that CRM-geothermal knowledge is not only disseminated, but embedded in Europe's education landscape, thereby contributing to societal awareness, professional training, and sustainable resource management for decades to come.

3 GEOSCIENCE EDUCATION AT SECONDARY SCHOOL LEVEL

Geoscience, or Earth science, is a general term that relates various disciplines for the study of the Earth-ecosystem. Understanding the earth's mechanisms is essential for sustaining life on our planet, as geoscience plays a critical role in managing our primary resources: energy, minerals, water, and food. While the term "geoscience" is often used interchangeably with "geology," the latter is more specific to foundational and precise study of the Earth compared with the larger encompassing term of geoscience.

Despite its significance for life on Earth, geoscience is generally not taught as a standalone subject at the secondary school level in Europe. Instead, geological concepts are integrated into broader subjects such as Geography, Physics, Chemistry, or General Science. The extent to which geology is emphasised within these subjects varies considerably across European countries, reflecting differences in national curricula, educational policies, and cultural priorities.

3.1 CURRENT STATUS IN EUROPE

Several organisations have warned that most secondary school curricula do not include a substantial geology component. Inadequate geological knowledge affects not only university students but also the citizens who finish their secondary studies without having learned any basic geological concepts.

Earth sciences play a key role in developing higher-order thinking skills, helping learners overcome cognitive barriers to spatial and temporal thinking, retrospection, and understanding complex phenomena. It fosters integration across disciplines and nurtures systems thinking. Earth sciences equip citizens to make informed decisions about energy, water, and resource conservation. Those who understand Earth's processes are better positioned to act scientifically and responsibly.

In the following, the status of earth science education in Europe is discussed based on the results of different representative surveys.

3.1.1 Survey by the EFG Panel of Experts on Education

In 2015, the EFG Panel of Experts on Education conducted a survey on geology education within public schools across 11 European countries (Croatia, Czech Republic, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Portugal, Russia, Slovenia, Spain, UK and Ukraine) (Hartai, 2016). In these countries, geology is incorporated into the compulsory curriculum, primarily within the subjects of Natural Sciences and Geography. It is mostly taught by geography teachers or general science teachers (*Figure 1*), and the age of students learning geology typically ranges from 11 to 16 years.

It is concluded that generally, suitable teaching materials are scarce, consisting mostly of textbooks, worksheets, or digital educational content. Optional geology-related courses are offered only in a limited number of schools. Assessments of students' geological knowledge are rare and usually restricted to local information. Geology outreach programmes are mainly provided by professional organisations.

3.1.2 Survey by IGEO

In 2015-16, the International Geoscience Education Organisation (IGEO) conducted a survey in 27 countries worldwide on the global perspectives of Earth science education. The European Union was represented by eight countries in the survey: Austria, Bulgaria, England, France, Germany, Italy, Portugal, Spain. Results of the survey are summarised by Greco & Almberg (2018).

Figure 1: Teacher backgrounds in geoscience education at secondary school level (based on EFG’s 2015 survey).

In most of the listed European countries, geology is taught as a part of physical geography. In Austria, ‘Geography’ was changed to ‘Geography and Economic Studies’ which highly reduced the allocation for physical geography. However, major geoscientific content is embedded in the Austrian biology curriculum.

In Bulgaria, before 1965, geology was a stand-alone subject but now it is included in geography. In England, geology is part of the English National Geography Curriculum, compulsory for 5–14-years old students. Optional geology examination courses are available to some students aged 14-18.

In France and Italy, school systems attempt to direct interest towards geosciences, but the turn towards a more investigative approach or problem-based learning, with adequate laboratory supports, still needs time.

In Germany, there is a high diversity of curricula due to the German federalism and the early separation of students into different types of schools. Earth science content is mostly taught within geography. Some schools offer Earth sciences as electives or optional working groups.

In Spain, geology is included in the broader “Natural Science” subject, and forms a very limited part of the curricula.

In Portugal, teaching Earth sciences in basic and secondary education in Portugal has a long tradition. In the lower classes, Earth sciences is taught in the frame of Environmental Studies. In the 2nd Cycle education Earth science is included in Natural Sciences. The discipline of Natural Sciences, in the 7th grade, is entirely dedicated to Earth Sciences.

3.1.3 Surveys by UNESCO and IGEO

UNESCO and IGEO conducted four worldwide surveys on geoscience education between 2000 and 2017 (King et al., 2021). The most recent survey collected data from 51 countries, representing more than half of the world's population. The findings revealed that while most countries (75%) had established national standards related to Earth sciences, these standards were either not followed or were entirely absent in more than half of the surveyed countries. Furthermore, only about 25% of the countries with standardized assessments included Earth science-specific questions.

Most Earth science teachers are non-specialists, and the support provided to them through courses and professional development is generally insufficient. The quality of Earth science teaching materials

ranges from moderate to poor. However, there is substantial global support for informal Earth science education, with enthusiastic groups of educators striving to improve the rather bleak state of formal education.

Strategies being implemented include publishing an international syllabus with free-to-download supporting textbooks, providing websites with high-quality interactive teaching materials, promoting interactive geoscience education through national champions, and offering global support for these initiatives.

Table 1: Overview of international surveys on geoscience education in European secondary schools

Year	Organisation / Project	Countries Covered	Key Findings	Relevance for CRM-geothermal
2015	EFG Panel of Experts on Education (Hartai 2016)	11 European countries (e.g. Croatia, Czech Rep., Greece, Hungary, Italy, Spain, UK)	Geology taught mainly within geography/natural sciences; usually delivered by non-specialist teachers (mainly geography); few optional courses; limited teaching materials.	Confirms weak curricular position of geoscience and highlights the need for teacher support and better resources.
2016	IGEO survey (Greco & Almberg 2018)	8 EU countries (Austria, Bulgaria, England, France, Germany, Italy, Portugal, Spain)	Wide diversity in curricula; geology often reduced to a subset of physical geography; stand-alone courses rare; content and teaching quality uneven.	Shows fragmentation across Europe and provides a baseline for harmonisation efforts.
2000–2017	UNESCO–IGEO surveys (King et al. 2021)	51 countries worldwide (incl. EU states)	75% had Earth science standards, but in over half they were not implemented; Earth science teachers often non-specialists; poor-quality teaching materials; strong role of informal education.	Demonstrates systemic barriers and the importance of informal/alternative educational pathways.
2020	ENGIE project survey (Johansson et al. 2020)	21 European countries, ~750 teachers	Strong national/regional variation; Earth science integrated into natural sciences or geography; teaching resources dominated by textbooks/worksheets; some use of VR/AR; museums and geoparks play a role.	Highlights both the challenges (curricular inconsistency) and opportunities (digital tools, informal partners) relevant to CRM-geothermal outreach.

3.1.4 Survey by the ENGIE project

In 2020, as part of the ENGIE project (<https://learn.engieproject.eu/>), a survey was conducted involving 750 teachers from 21 European countries to assess geoscience education at secondary school level (Johansson et al., 2020). The findings reveal that approaches to Earth science education vary significantly within the European Union, due to differences in education systems. Compulsory schooling ages are also different (e.g., up to age 16 in France and Spain, and age 18 in Portugal).

In some EU countries, national standards or curricula are established by governments (e.g., Czech Republic, England, Finland, Hungary, Portugal), while others provide regional guidelines (e.g., Germany, France, Scotland). During the first 3–4 years of primary school, Earth science is typically integrated with biology and social science. From the 5th grade onward, it is mainly taught within

geography and natural science subjects. In secondary school (ages 12–14+), Earth science becomes less compulsory and is primarily taught within geography or natural science, with some optional courses available later (e.g., geology in the UK, France, and Portugal).

Teacher’s specialisation also varies. Teachers of natural science, biology (e.g., Czech Republic, Portugal), chemistry (e.g., England), general science (e.g., Norway), Earth science (e.g., Czech Republic), or geography (e.g., Hungary) can teach geology. Textbooks and worksheets remain the primary teaching tools, though interactive resources such as Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) are increasingly used. Museums, national parks, and interactive science centres also play a role in Earth science education.

The key findings of the surveys and the relevance for the CRM-geothermal project are summarised in *Table 1*. From the surveys, it can be concluded that in a very few countries, there is strong evidence that Earth systems education can achieve its potential and offer models for doing so. However, this potential is not widely realised. Globally, Earth science education remains low-profile. Geoscience is mostly taught to younger students by general science or geography teachers with limited Earth science expertise. As a stand-alone subject for high schoolers (16–18 years), Earth Science is offered in only a few countries

3.2 INTEREST OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN GEOSCIENCE

In more recent years, research on students’ attitudes toward learning is increasing, but geology remains relatively underexplored in this context.

The GEOschools project revealed insights into the interest of 14–16-year-old students in geosciences (Fermeli et al. 2015). A comparative review of geoscience curricula was made across five countries (Austria, Greece, Portugal, Italy, and Spain). Surveys were administered in 20 Greek schools (554 pupils) and 7 Spanish schools (155 pupils). Results show that topics such as natural hazards and palaeontology attract the most student interest (*Figure 2*). Teaching strategies also significantly influence engagement. Greek students showed more interest in geosciences than their Spanish peers.

Figure 2: Student interest in different geoscience topics (based on findings from the GEOschools and ENGIE surveys).

These results suggest a strong link between student interest and topics with high social relevance, such as mass extinctions, dinosaurs, geological disasters, and human evolution. This raises the question of whether curricula should adapt to emphasise these areas of interest rather than sticking rigidly to traditional academic structures. There is also a challenge: while media-friendly topics draw attention, deeper scientific understanding often remains limited. The goal should be to blend solid academic content with engaging, real-world connections, making geosciences both informative and enjoyable for students.

In 2020, a study was published on the attitudes of 1,641 Spanish secondary students towards geology compared to other sciences (Zamalloa & Sanz 2020). Results showed that geology was viewed more negatively. Students found geology boring and uninteresting, though not particularly difficult. These attitudes were not linked to gender, school type, or demographics. Instead, academic factors played a larger role. The study suggests that to improve attitudes, geology education should focus on engaging topics and make stronger connections between classroom content and real-world relevance.

The ENGIE project also assessed the interest of secondary school students in geoscience (*Figure 2*) (Johansson, 2020). Nearly 5,000 students from 20 European countries participated in the study.

The survey evaluated students' familiarity with geoscience and their interest in pursuing it as a profession. The results indicate that almost half of the participants consider themselves familiar with geoscience, and more than one-fourth know someone working as a geoscience professional.

Furthermore, 21% of participants expressed interest in potentially working as a geoscience professional. Their career choices are influenced more by rational factors, particularly expected educational achievements, rather than social factors such as encouragement from friends, teachers, or parents.

3.3 BEST PRACTICES IN TEACHING GEOSCIENCE

3.3.1 Theoretical framework

In Europe, diverse national curricula, pedagogical traditions, and sociocultural contexts influence how geology is taught. Contemporary geoscience education is grounded in constructivist and socio-constructivist learning theories, which posit that students learn most effectively through active engagement and social interaction within meaningful contexts. These approaches support inquiry-based, experiential, and collaborative learning environments—well aligned with the field-based and interdisciplinary nature of geoscience (Ryker & McConnell, 2017b; Cheek, 2020).

Spatial thinking plays a central role in geoscience due to the discipline's emphasis on visualising three-dimensional structures, geological timescales, and abstract spatial patterns. Developing students' spatial skills is essential for comprehending complex Earth systems, such as tectonic processes and sedimentary layering. Educators are encouraged to scaffold content using tools such as cross-sectional models, digital terrain maps, and virtual globes to aid in the interpretation of geoscientific representations (Liben & Titus, 2018; Gagnier et al., 2017).

Education for Sustainable Development (ESD), as promoted by UNESCO, provides a unifying framework that connects geoscience learning with sustainability principles. ESD in geoscience fosters competencies such as systems thinking, critical analysis, and ethical reasoning about environmental challenges such as resource use, climate change, and natural hazards (UNESCO, 2020). The integration of ESD also aligns geoscience education with broader societal goals outlined in the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goal 4.7 (UNESCO, 2020).

Recent European initiatives have highlighted the value of experiential learning in geoscience, particularly through out-of-classroom activities such as field trips, interactive simulations, and school-based investigations. These methods have been shown to improve student motivation, conceptual understanding, and long-term retention of geological principles (Makri et al., 2020a). Furthermore, such practices can help make geoscience education more inclusive and adaptable to diverse learning environments.

3.3.2 Effective pedagogical approaches and methods

Effective pedagogy in geosciences emphasises student-centred, inquiry-driven learning that mirrors the investigative nature of the discipline. Teaching approaches that actively engage students in constructing their own understanding tend to yield deeper conceptual understanding and long-term retention. Central to this is the integration of real-world contexts, where learners grapple with authentic problems, fostering both scientific thinking and relevance to societal issues. Experiential learning, particularly through fieldwork, plays a critical role by connecting theoretical knowledge to tangible observations, thereby strengthening spatial reasoning and interpretive skills. The use of digital tools, such as geographic information systems and interactive simulations, further enhances learning by making abstract processes visible and manipulable. Additionally, effective instruction in geosciences often builds progressively on prior knowledge, providing supports that help students tackle complex systems and interdisciplinary content (Figure 3). The inclusive and reflective teaching practice, sensitive to diverse backgrounds and perspectives, ensures broader accessibility and engagement, ultimately cultivating both scientific literacy and environmental awareness.

Figure 3: Effective pedagogical approaches and methods in geoscience education

Below, the key methods of effective pedagogy are detailed.

Inquiry-based and problem-based learning (PBL),

Inquiry-based learning (IBL) and PBL are core strategies in effective science education. They promote critical thinking, engagement, and understanding by allowing students to investigate real-world problems and simulate scientific processes (Pedaste et al., 2015). In geoscience, PBL often includes exploring case studies of natural hazards, climate events, or resource management issues. These methods are supported by European initiatives like SAILS (Strategies for Assessment of Inquiry Learning in Science) and PARRISE (Promoting Attainment of Responsible Research and Innovation in Science Education), which emphasise student-led investigations aligned with socio-scientific issues.

Use of models, visualizations, and digital tools

The integration of digital tools, models, and visualizations has become increasingly prevalent in geoscience education to address the challenges of teaching abstract concepts. Educators are leveraging technologies such as Geographic Information Systems (GIS), three-dimensional (3D) models, augmented reality (AR), and virtual field trips (VFTs) to enhance spatial reasoning and student

engagement. GIS platforms enable students to analyse and interpret spatial data, fostering a deeper understanding of Earth's systems. The GEOTHNK project, a European initiative, developed GIS-supported learning environments that promote systems thinking and data analysis skills among students (Kavouras et al., 2016). These environments allow learners to visualise complex geospatial relationships and processes, facilitating a more comprehensive grasp of geoscientific phenomena.

3D models serve as effective tools for visualising geological structures and processes that are otherwise difficult to comprehend through two-dimensional representations. By interacting with 3D models, students can explore the spatial relationships and temporal evolution of geological formations, enhancing their conceptual understanding (Gagnier et al., 2017).

AR technologies overlay digital information onto the physical world, providing immersive learning experiences that bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and real-world applications. For instance, the EDU-MAT COPERNICUS platform integrates AR with satellite data to support mathematics and geoscience education, improving spatial reasoning and cognitive engagement among primary school students (Kaźmierczak et al., 2025).

Complementing these technological solutions, initiatives like Earth Learning Idea (ELI) provide educators with a repository of free, inquiry-based activities designed to simulate geological processes and phenomena in classroom settings. These resources employ simple materials and hands-on experiments to model complex Earth systems, making geoscience education more accessible and engaging for students, particularly in resource-limited environments.

Outdoor learning and field-based education

Fieldtrips and field-based education are essential components of effective Earth science instruction at the secondary school level, as they provide experiential learning opportunities that significantly enhance students' understanding of geological processes and environmental systems. Unlike traditional classroom instruction, field-based learning immerses students in real-world contexts where they can directly observe, collect, and analyse geological data. This experiential approach has been shown to foster deeper conceptual understanding and increase student engagement and motivation (Boyle et al., 2007).

Recent studies have reinforced the pedagogical value of field experiences. For example, Stokes and Boyle (2015) found that secondary students who participated in fieldtrips demonstrated improved spatial thinking and better retention of complex Earth science concepts. Field-based learning also supports the development of key scientific practices, such as observation, hypothesis formation, data interpretation, and collaboration (Stokes et al., 2011). Furthermore, outdoor learning environments offer opportunities for place-based education, enabling students to connect scientific content with local environmental and geological features, thus fostering environmental stewardship and scientific literacy (King, 2008; Remmen & Frøyland, 2015).

In addition to cognitive benefits, fieldtrips can promote socio-emotional learning and inclusion by accommodating diverse learning styles and encouraging peer interaction in less formal settings (Remmen & Frøyland, 2015). Given these wide-ranging advantages, integrating field-based components into Earth science curricula is critical for developing scientifically literate and environmentally conscious citizens capable of engaging with global challenges such as climate change and natural resource management.

Virtual field trips

The digital transformation of geoscience education has accelerated since 2020, driven by the need for remote learning solutions and the integration of innovative technologies. Bouziat et al. (2020b) highlight this shift, emphasising the adoption of digital tools such as virtual reality (VR), machine

learning, and gamification to enhance geoscience training. These tools not only modernise educational approaches but also attract students from computer science backgrounds, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration.

Virtual field trips (VFTs) have emerged as a particularly valuable tool in this context. By leveraging technologies such as Geographic Information Systems (GIS), 3D modelling, and interactive platforms, VFTs allow students to explore geological sites remotely. These virtual experiences can simulate the observational and analytical aspects of fieldwork, thereby supporting the development of geoscientific skills. Moreover, VFTs can serve as preparatory exercises for in-person field trips, enhancing students' readiness and maximising the educational value of subsequent on-site experiences (Evelpidou et al., 2022).

Vandelly et al (2024) also emphasised the advantages of virtual fieldtrips as they include an opportunity to examine places otherwise difficult or impossible to access. It may also become an important component of education, fostering a better understanding of processes and landforms, geohazard awareness, and an appreciation of geoheritage.

Socio-scientific issues and interdisciplinary learning

Teaching geoscience through the lens of socio-scientific issues (SSI) fosters relevance and civic engagement. Topics such as mining, seismic risks, or climate change provide interdisciplinary entry points and promote reflective thinking. SSI-based instruction aligns with Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) and encourages students to consider ethical, cultural, and political dimensions of Earth science topics. Recent studies have highlighted the effectiveness of SSI in enhancing students' critical thinking and decision-making skills. For instance, a systematic review by Högström et al. (2024) found that SSI pedagogy in primary and secondary education promotes higher-order thinking and scientific literacy. Another review emphasised the importance of integrating real-world problems to make science education more relevant and engaging (Viehmann, 2024).

Moreover, incorporating SSI into science lessons has been shown to encourage interdisciplinary learning. A scoping review by Capkinoglu et al. (2020) revealed that SSI topics often intersect with environmental, genetic, and health-related concerns, providing opportunities for students to explore the interconnectedness of science and society. This approach not only deepens understanding but also prepares students to address complex societal challenges through scientific inquiry.

In the context of geoscience education, integrating SSI can be particularly impactful. By examining issues such as climate change and natural resource management, students can develop a more comprehensive understanding of the Earth's systems and the human activities that influence them. This holistic perspective is essential for fostering informed and responsible citizens capable of making decisions that contribute to sustainable development.

Formative Assessment and Feedback

Formative assessment and feedback are increasingly recognized as pivotal components in enhancing geoscience education, particularly within inquiry-based learning (IBL) frameworks. These strategies facilitate the monitoring of student understanding, provide timely feedback, and support the development of self-regulated learning skills essential for comprehending complex geoscientific concepts (Veugen et al. 2021).

In geoscience education, formative assessment methods such as concept mapping, reflective writing, and diagnostic quizzes have been effectively employed to identify students' preconceptions and guide instructional adjustments. For instance, Grob et al. (2017) demonstrated that peer-assessment in Swiss primary classrooms not only enhanced students' understanding of scientific concepts but also

promoted self-regulation and motivation. Similarly, Correia and Harrison (2020) found that teachers' beliefs about inquiry-based learning significantly influenced their formative assessment practices, impacting students' autonomy and engagement in science lessons.

European research initiatives have piloted innovative tools to evaluate IBL, emphasizing the integration of formative assessment into classroom practices. Grob et al. (2015) highlighted the use of structured formative assessment methods, including rubrics and digital portfolios, to support students' competencies in inquiry-based science education. These tools have been instrumental in providing continuous feedback, fostering students' critical thinking, and enhancing their ability to apply geoscientific knowledge in real-world contexts.

3.3.3 Case studies and projects in Europe

The GEOschools project, supported by the EU Comenius Programme, aimed to enhance geoscience education across European secondary schools by developing innovative teaching resources and promoting interdisciplinary learning. Initiated in 2010, the project brought together geoscientists, educators, and institutions from countries including Greece, Spain, Italy, Portugal, and Austria to bridge the gap between scientific knowledge and school curricula (GEOschools, n.d.). A central outcome of GEOschools was the establishment of a “Framework on Geosciences Literacy Principles,” designed to harmonize geoscience education while respecting local geological contexts (Rodrigues et al., 2013b). This framework informed the creation of five educational modules, emphasising field-based learning in geoparks and geosites. Additionally, GEOschools developed multilingual glossaries of geological terms to support students' comprehension and facilitate the integration of geoscience topics into various subjects (GEOschools, n.d.). The project also emphasised teacher training, providing resources and workshops to enhance educators' ability to deliver geoscience content effectively.

Earth Learning Idea (ELI) is a global geoscience education initiative that offers a comprehensive collection of free, multilingual teaching activities designed to make Earth science accessible and engaging, particularly in resource-limited educational settings. Since its inception in 2007, ELI has expanded its repository to over 450 activities, many accompanied by teaching videos and extension ideas, all freely downloadable from its website. These activities emphasize inquiry-based learning and critical thinking, often requiring only simple materials, making them adaptable for diverse classroom environments.

ELI's resources are translated into multiple languages, including Spanish, German, Portuguese, Polish, Slovak, and Chinese, facilitating their integration into various national curricula and promoting global reach. The initiative also incorporates the Cognitive Acceleration through Science Education (CASE) approach, providing professional development workshops and teaching videos to enhance educators' pedagogical skills. With over 7 million downloads worldwide, ELI has become a valuable tool for educators aiming to foster a deeper understanding of Earth sciences among students (Earth Learning Idea).

The European Geoparks Network (EGN) plays a crucial role in Earth Science education by providing unique learning opportunities and promoting the appreciation of geological heritage. Geoparks act as outdoor classrooms, offering hands-on experiences, field trips, and educational resources for all age groups. They integrate geological knowledge with cultural and historical contexts, fostering a holistic understanding of the Earth and its environment. The number of geoparks is continuously increasing.

The European Geoparks Network (EGN), an integral component of UNESCO's Global Geoparks initiative, has significantly advanced geoscience education since 2020 by intertwining geological heritage with sustainable development and community engagement. These geoparks serve as dynamic

platforms for experiential learning, fostering a deeper understanding of the Earth's processes and promoting environmental stewardship. A European Geopark supports environmental education, training and the development of scientific research in the various disciplines within Earth Sciences, the improvement of the natural environment and sustainable development policies (Zouros, 2004).

One notable initiative is the 4GEON project, launched in 2022, which connects geoparks across four continents through playful Earth heritage education. This project emphasizes informal, interactive learning tailored to individual geoparks, combining digital resources with outdoor activities to engage youth and local communities in understanding geological features and their relevance to daily life (UNESCO 2024).

Additionally, the Estrela UNESCO Global Geopark in Portugal has implemented the Science and Education Network for Sustainability, aiming to promote knowledge of the region through various scientific areas. This network supports applied research and citizen science initiatives, fostering a deeper connection between the local population and their geological heritage (Gomes et al., 2020). These efforts underscore the EGN's commitment to enhancing geoscience education by leveraging the unique geological features of each geopark, promoting sustainable development, and fostering global collaboration.

Table 2: Examples of best practices in geoscience teaching in European secondary schools

Approach / Project	Country / Region	Key Features	Benefits / Lessons Learned
GEOschools project (Comenius Programme)	Austria, Greece, Portugal, Italy, Spain	Developed interdisciplinary modules, field-based learning in geoparks, multilingual glossaries.	Enhanced student engagement; teacher training supported stronger integration of geoscience in curricula.
Earth Learning Idea (ELI)	International, incl. European partners	Open-access repository with >450 multilingual activities; simple classroom experiments.	Democratizes access to high-quality teaching materials; promotes inquiry-based learning even in resource-limited schools.
European Geoparks Network (EGN)	28 European countries	Geoparks as “outdoor classrooms” offering field trips, local case studies, and citizen science.	Strong experiential learning; connects local heritage with sustainability and SDG education.
ENGIE project (EU Horizon 2020)	21 European countries	Surveyed 750 teachers and engaged ~5,000 students, especially girls; offered teacher training modules.	Demonstrated gender-sensitive approaches; increased interest in geoscience careers among female students.
Virtual field trips (e.g. TRiPGiFT project, Geological Survey of Belgium)	Belgium, EU-wide	360° immersive virtual tours of geosites and mining areas.	Overcomes cost/logistical barriers of fieldwork; increases accessibility and inclusivity of geoscience education.
BetterGeoEdu (Minecraft modification)	Sweden	Gamified learning tool simulating geology, mineral resources, and sustainable mining.	High engagement of digital-native students; links entertainment with real-world geoscience concepts.

The Geological Survey of Belgium, in collaboration with the Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences, offers 360° virtual field trips that showcase significant geosites, such as the UNESCO Global Geopark Famenne-Ardenne. These immersive experiences highlight the importance of geological sites in understanding subsurface potential and promote science outreach by making geological knowledge accessible to a broader audience (Geological Survey of Belgium).

Another good example is the TRiPGiFT project, which focuses on training pupils in geosciences by utilising virtual field trips. It offers open simulators of three geoscience virtual field trips, including marble quarrying from antiquity to the present, fluvial and tectonic geomorphology, and other geological themes. These virtual excursions aim to enhance students' understanding of geological processes and promote interest in geosciences through interactive and engaging digital platforms (Spyrou, 2023).

Gamification can also be a means to engage young learners. An example is BetterGeoEdu, a project that utilizes BetterGeo – a Minecraft modification developed by the Geological Survey of Sweden – to simulate realistic geological processes, mineral formations, and sustainable mining practices. This approach aligns with the EU's Digital Education Action Plan, emphasising digital readiness and the integration of technical tools in teaching. By embedding educational content within a familiar and engaging platform, BetterGeoEdu aims to inspire creativity and learning, making geology accessible and appealing to the digital-native generation. Such innovative methods can play a crucial role in shaping future industry workers and policymakers, fostering a more informed and sustainable approach to raw material consumption (Westrin et al., 2020).

3.3.4 Main challenges to follow best practices

Despite positive developments, several challenges hinder effective geoscience education in Europe (*Table 3*). These challenges are characterised below.

A significant challenge to implementing best practices in geoscience education at the secondary level is the lack of teacher preparedness, both in terms of content knowledge and pedagogical expertise. Geoscience is an interdisciplinary field that requires familiarity with complex Earth systems, spatial reasoning, and dynamic processes – domains often underrepresented in general science teacher training programmes. Many secondary school science teachers come from backgrounds in biology, chemistry, or physics and have limited exposure to Earth science, resulting in gaps in their ability to effectively teach geoscience concepts (King, 2013). This lack of specialisation hinders the adoption of inquiry-based and experiential methods – such as fieldwork, model-based instruction, and digital simulations – that are central to effective geoscience teaching (Ryker & McConnell, 2017a).

Furthermore, the pedagogical approaches in contemporary geoscience education, grounded in constructivist and socio-constructivist theories, demand skills in framing student learning, managing open-ended investigations, and integrating digital tools such as GIS and 3D visualisation software (Liben & Titus, 2018). Without targeted professional development, teachers may lack confidence and competence to implement these strategies. The situation gets worse by the limited availability of continuous professional development opportunities focused on Earth sciences, particularly in regions where geoscience is not a compulsory subject in the curriculum (Stokes et al., 2011b).

Addressing this challenge requires sustained investment in teacher education programmes that emphasise both geoscience content and innovative teaching methodologies. Initiatives such as Earth Learning Idea and GEOSCHOOL have made steps in this direction by offering resources and workshops to support teacher training (Rodrigues et al., 2013a), yet systemic support remains essential to ensure that teachers are equipped to meet the evolving demands of geoscience education.

The ENGIE project, in which EFG played a major role, also offered training for secondary school teachers, with the involvement of EFG's Panels of Experts. The aim was to help teachers in teaching geoscience in an attractive and engaging way (<https://learn.engieproject.eu/>).

Table 3: Challenges and barriers in teaching geoscience at secondary school level

Challenge	Description	Implications	Potential Solutions
Teacher preparedness	Many teachers are trained in geography, biology, or general science, with limited background in geosciences. Lack of confidence in fieldwork or use of digital tools.	Limits quality of instruction; discourages innovative methods such as inquiry-based learning.	Provide targeted teacher training; develop professional development modules; strengthen collaboration with universities and professional associations.
Curricular integration	Geoscience often fragmented into other subjects (geography, biology), rarely taught as a stand-alone subject.	Leads to superficial coverage of key concepts (plate tectonics, resource cycles, hazards).	Embed geoscience more explicitly in curricula; align with Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) and SDGs.
Resource limitations	Field trips, labs, and digital resources are costly and not equally available across schools.	Creates inequality between schools; reduces opportunities for experiential learning.	Promote open-access teaching materials (e.g. Earth Learning Idea); use virtual field trips and gamified tools; partner with geoparks and museums.
Policy support	Earth sciences often marginalised in national education policies compared to biology, physics, chemistry.	Restricts instructional time and funding; weakens public awareness of geoscience.	Advocate for stronger policy recognition at national and EU level; link to Green Deal, Raw Materials Act, and SDG priorities.
Student perception	Geoscience sometimes perceived as “boring” or less relevant compared to other sciences.	Reduces motivation to pursue geoscience careers.	Emphasise engaging topics (natural hazards, climate change, fossils); connect lessons to real-world challenges and sustainability issues.

A persistent challenge in implementing best practices in geoscience education lies in its marginal status within the secondary school curriculum. Compared to biology, chemistry, and physics, geoscience often receives significantly less instructional time and institutional attention, resulting in limited student exposure to Earth systems and processes (King, 2013). In many educational systems, geoscience is not offered as a standalone subject but is instead fragmented across other disciplines such as geography, environmental science, or general science. While this integration has the potential to provide interdisciplinary perspectives, it can also dilute the subject’s core content and hinder systematic concept development (UNESCO, 2020).

The interdisciplinary nature of Earth sciences – linking physical geography, ecology, chemistry, and physics – makes it well suited for integration into related subjects. However, effective integration requires careful curricular design to ensure that key geoscientific concepts are explicitly addressed rather than being treated as peripheral topics. Without structured frameworks and teacher guidance, integration risks becoming superficial, leaving students with fragmented knowledge and limited understanding of complex systems such as plate tectonics, geohazards, or Earth’s resource cycles (Ryker & McConnell, 2017a).

Recent efforts such as the GEOSCHOOL project have demonstrated that integrated models can succeed when curricular materials, teacher training, and institutional support are aligned (Rodrigues et al., 2013a). Moreover, aligning geoscience education with themes from Education for Sustainable

Development (ESD) can increase its relevance and visibility within broader curricular goals, especially when linked to real-world challenges such as climate change or natural disasters (UNESCO, 2020). Nonetheless, to make integration effective and meaningful, geoscience must be intentionally embedded within cross-disciplinary curricula, supported by coherent standards and adequate instructional time.

A major barrier to the effective implementation of best practices in secondary geoscience education is the unequal distribution of educational resources. Fieldwork, laboratory experiments, and digital tools are fundamental components of geoscience teaching, yet many schools – particularly those in rural or economically disadvantaged areas – lack the infrastructure and funding to support these practices (Stokes et al., 2011; Evelpidou et al., 2022). The resource-intensive nature of experiential learning, including transportation for field trips, specialised laboratory equipment, or access to Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and virtual reality tools, can worsen existing educational inequalities, limiting students' opportunities to engage with Earth science content (Makri et al., 2020b).

These inequalities not only affect students' cognitive outcomes but also their interest and engagement in geosciences. Without opportunities to explore real-world geological contexts or interact with spatial data, learners may struggle to grasp abstract processes such as plate tectonics, erosion, or geohazard dynamics (Liben & Titus, 2018). Moreover, schools lacking access to high-quality teaching materials or professional development for educators often fall behind in adopting innovative, inquiry-based pedagogies that are essential for effective geoscience instruction.

To address these inequities, open-access educational resources, such as those provided by Earth Learning Idea, and digital platforms offering virtual field trips have emerged as promising solutions. These tools can simulate geological phenomena and provide interactive experiences that approximate field-based learning (Bouziat et al., 2020). In parallel, partnerships between schools and geoparks have proven effective in facilitating access to authentic geological environments, offering place-based learning opportunities even in resource-constrained settings (Gomes et al., 2020). These strategies contribute to democratising geoscience education and ensuring that all students, regardless of context, can develop the spatial and systems thinking skills required for scientific literacy and environmental management.

A key challenge to advancing best practices in geoscience education lies in the limited policy recognition it receives at both, national and European, levels. Despite the growing relevance of Earth sciences to pressing global issues – such as climate change, resource management, and natural hazard mitigation – geoscience remains underrepresented in educational policy frameworks when compared to other STEM disciplines (King, 2013; UNESCO, 2020). This marginalisation has direct effects on curriculum design, teacher training, and resource allocation, ultimately constraining efforts to embed geoscience within broader educational agendas focused on sustainability and scientific competence.

Effective geoscience education plays a critical role in fostering competencies aligned with the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 4.7, which emphasises the importance of Education for Sustainable Development (ESD). Yet, in many European countries, policy support for integrating ESD into science curricula lacks clarity regarding Earth science content (Hofman-Bergholm, 2021). As a result, opportunities to teach key geoscientific concepts, such as systems thinking, spatial analysis, and human-Earth interactions are often missed or superficially addressed in other subjects like geography or environmental science.

Strengthening policy support requires coordinated action at both national and EU levels. European initiatives such as the GEOschools project and the Earth Learning Idea platform demonstrate the potential of policy-backed programmes to promote geoscience knowledge through teacher

development, open-access resources, and curriculum innovation (Rodrigues et al., 2013). Moreover, integrating geoscience into science education strategies under the European Green Deal and Digital Education Action Plan could reinforce its role in preparing students for future environmental and societal challenges. A robust policy framework is thus essential to elevate the status of geoscience education and align it with broader educational, environmental, and technological priorities.

4 ASSESSMENT OF THE CRM-GEOTHERMAL VIDEO CONTEST

There is strong scientific evidence showing that contests and competitions are effective tools for boosting students' interest in science and engagement with STEM fields (Miller et al. 2017). Contests that invite participants to produce their own science videos, such as the European SciChallenge programme, encourage creativity, peer-to-peer communication, and ownership over STEM topics. By generating video content, students build confidence, sharpen science communication skills, and identify as science creators rather than passive learners (Dermutz & Scheuch 2016).

In line with that, in 2024, the CRM-geothermal consortium launched a video contest on geothermal and critical raw materials for 12-18-year-olds in Europe. Participants were invited to address any of the following subjects: (1) the key role of geothermal in fighting climate change, (2) the importance of critical raw materials in our everyday life and (3) the importance of mining in their area. In this section, metrics and their metadata collected during the CRM-geothermal Video Contest are analysed and presented in graphs. The main purpose is to identify trends and potential relationships that have an impact on engagement.

The CRM-geothermal Affiliated Entities (18 of the National Associations of the European Federation of Geologists, representing different European countries) supported the promotion of the video contest. Their support with local contacts and in national languages was key to promoting this activity.

In total 1,598 schools were contacted (where data was available) resulting in 16 videos being submitted. From this, five finalists were selected. Countries such as Italy contacted 485 schools but had only 1 video submission (*Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.*⁴), possibly indicating a lack of follow-up engagement. The Portuguese Association of Geologists contacted 649 schools and 835 teachers. Portugal and the UK had the highest number of submissions (four each). The Affiliated Entity from Portugal (Portuguese Association of Geologists) was one of the most active in promoting the contest. Although there was no Affiliated Entity from the UK, intensive promotion through the project and EFG communication channels played a key role in engaging teenagers there.

Some countries (e.g. Slovenia, Bulgaria) showed better conversion with fewer schools contacted. This suggests that direct outreach is not always a clear predictor of participation, and other factors, such as engagement methods or school enthusiasm, may have a larger role. This is in agreement with what has been observed in other projects in which EFG is participating. The ENGIE project (<https://www.engieproject.eu/>) was a success in engaging schools, but the effect has been in a declining mode in other projects such as CEEGS and CRM-Geothermal. Better targeting or follow-up might significantly improve engagement.

Figure 4: Video submissions against schools contacted per country, bars show the number of video submissions per country, red line with dots indicates how many schools were contacted in that country.

Figure 5 presents the total impressions/views per platform used for the contest. LinkedIn had the highest reach, with 6,450 views, followed by X, with 5,630 views. Instagram and TikTok, although youth-oriented, had lower reach (1,757 and 1,342 respectively), possibly due to engagement limitations. However, another factor might be algorithm optimisation when using the aforementioned platforms. The time of postage and frequency of posts from the poster have significant impacts on how the platforms perform. Usually, the system ranks higher frequent posters and thus it presents their posts quicker and frequent.

Figure 5: Social media impact of CRM-Geothermal Video Contest.

Most participants were aged 16 and 17 (7 each). There was moderate participation from younger teens, with a peak at age 12 (6 students), likely driven by class-based team submissions (*Figure 6*).

Figure 6: Age distribution of participants.

Of the participants, 73% were female (19 participants), with the remaining 27% being male (7 participants). This suggests the contest resonated significantly more with female students.

After reviewing the data metrics from social media dissemination some highlights provided clues that may have driven engagement and audience response. The videos with the highest number of views received more impressions and longer total watch times. However, this visibility is also related to the underlying algorithms of social media, which suggest that the more frequently a video appears in users’ feeds or searches, the more likely it is to be watched and watched for longer durations. The data analysis indicates a strong correlation between high-performing videos and the number of new subscribers gained. On the same note, videos that relied heavily on external sources, such as links shared via WhatsApp or Facebook did not consistently achieve better performance. Although such channels can help spread content, they may not always have reached audiences specifically interested in geothermal or CRM topics, leading to limited viewer retention. This should be viewed from the perspective that the subject matter is highly specialised and thus the interest has a narrow spectrum of viewers who share the content. Future strategic promotion, combined with clearer data tracking, will shed light on better understanding the linkages and audience preferences.

In conclusion, some countries, such as Italy, contacted 485 schools but received only 1 submission, indicating that an arbitrary high number of contacts does not ensure engagement. LinkedIn and X outperformed Instagram and TikTok in raw impressions. This may imply that audience-platform mismatch might have limited actual contest visibility among youth and algorithm performance needs to be taken into account in future actions. Older teens, especially girls, are the most engaged demographic group. Future contests might leverage this by tailoring messaging to these groups.

The results of the CRM-geothermal video contest demonstrate both, the potential and the limitations of this form of youth engagement. With 26 participants from eight European countries submitting 16 videos, the contest successfully reached a diverse audience and engaged predominantly older teenagers, especially girls, in creative science communication. The social media campaign associated with the contest generated over 15,000 impressions across platforms and increased the project’s visibility among younger demographic groups, confirming the value of interactive and participatory approaches for outreach. Although participation numbers remained modest compared to the scale of promotion, the contest nonetheless provided a powerful platform for awareness-raising, allowing

students, teachers, and parents to reflect on the relevance of geothermal energy and critical raw materials in the context of the energy transition. For CRM-geothermal, the exercise has proven directly relevant to the project’s exploitation strategy, as it has illustrated effective ways to communicate complex topics to younger audiences, tested innovative engagement tools, and provided lessons for scaling up educational initiatives in schools and communities.

5 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS

Secondary schools play a decisive role in shaping awareness and attitudes toward Earth sciences, sustainability, and resource management. As the CRM-geothermal project has demonstrated, students are most engaged when geoscience topics are linked to real-world issues, such as climate change, energy transition, or the use of raw materials in everyday life. Yet, geoscience education remains fragmented across European curricula, often confined to subsets of geography or general science, with limited visibility of geothermal energy and critical raw materials. Teacher preparedness and access to resources are additional challenges. At the same time, student surveys confirm both strong interest in socially relevant topics and negative perceptions when content is taught in abstract or outdated ways.

Table 4: Recommendations for strengthening geoscience education in European secondary schools

Area	Recommendation	Key Actions	Expected Impact
Curricular integration	Embed geoscience more explicitly within existing subjects (geography, physics, chemistry, biology).	Link geothermal energy to climate change modules; integrate CRMs into chemistry/physics lessons; develop cross-disciplinary projects (e.g. battery life cycle).	Greater visibility of geoscience; stronger relevance to sustainability and daily life.
Pedagogical innovation	Apply inquiry-based, problem-based, and experiential learning approaches.	Use case studies, field trips, virtual field trips, and debates on socio-scientific issues; adopt gamified tools and simulations.	Increased student engagement and critical thinking; improved long-term retention.
Teacher training and resources	Strengthen teacher capacity and provide open-access materials.	Develop online/blended training modules; partner with universities and professional associations; expand CRM-geothermal teaching materials repository.	More confident and skilled teachers; consistent use of modern teaching approaches.
Student Engagement	Stimulate creativity and awareness through participatory formats.	Organise video, poster, or essay contests; promote peer-to-peer learning; leverage social media platforms; highlight geoscience career paths.	Higher motivation among students; improved perception of geoscience careers.
Partnerships and networks	Connect schools with external actors for expertise and resources.	Collaborate with museums, geoparks, universities, and industry; involve national geological societies; integrate into EU initiatives (e.g. Geoparks Network, Earth Learning Idea).	Enhanced experiential learning; access to cutting-edge knowledge; alignment with EU priorities.

Against this background, the recommendations for secondary schools outlined above aim to improve curricular integration, introduce modern pedagogical approaches, and strengthen teacher capacity (Table 4). They are directly aligned with the European Green Deal, the Critical Raw Materials Act, and the Sustainable Development Goals, while supporting the CRM-geothermal exploitation strategy to

raise awareness of sustainable raw material supply and renewable energy. The recommendations and the related key actions are detailed below.

5.1 CURRICULAR INTEGRATION

A first priority is to strengthen the place of geoscience in secondary school curricula. At present, geology is rarely taught as a stand-alone subject; instead, it is embedded within geography, natural sciences, or environmental studies. This integration can be effective if handled systematically, but in many cases geoscience topics remain peripheral. Curricular reform should therefore ensure that fundamental geoscience concepts are explicitly included and coherently linked to broader themes of sustainability and the energy transition.

Topics related to geothermal energy and critical raw materials provide excellent entry points for this integration. For instance, modules on climate change in geography can be extended with content on geothermal energy as a renewable solution, while chemistry classes can explore the life cycle of critical elements such as lithium, cobalt, or rare earths. Physics lessons may highlight geothermal heat as an application of thermodynamics, while ethics or social studies can address issues of raw material sourcing and circular economy. Cross-disciplinary projects, such as “The hidden journey of a smartphone battery,” can help students connect scientific concepts with their daily lives and with European policy goals.

By embedding such content into existing curricular structures, schools can make geoscience both relevant and engaging, without necessarily requiring additional teaching hours.

5.2 TEACHING APPROACHES AND PEDAGOGICAL INNOVATION

Curricular content alone is not enough to foster meaningful engagement. The methods used to deliver geoscience topics are equally important. Research and European pilot projects demonstrate that inquiry-based and problem-based learning (IBL, PBL) are particularly effective in stimulating curiosity and higher-order thinking. For example, students can investigate how geothermal plants operate, or debate the social implications of mining in their region, thereby developing both, scientific understanding and critical thinking.

Experiential learning is another key approach. Fieldwork has long been a cornerstone of geoscience education, and whenever possible schools should provide opportunities for students to explore local geological sites, geothermal facilities, or science museums. Where logistical or financial constraints limit such activities, virtual field trips and interactive digital simulations can provide accessible alternatives.

Digital innovation offers further opportunities. The use of GIS platforms, augmented and virtual reality (AR/VR), and gamified learning environments can bring abstract geological processes to life. Projects such as BetterGeoEdu (Minecraft modification) demonstrate how popular digital tools can be transformed into engaging educational platforms. Similarly, the CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas can be adapted into a teaching resource, offering students hands-on interaction with real data about geothermal systems and raw materials.

By combining inquiry-driven methods, experiential opportunities, and digital tools, teachers can make geoscience more attractive and relevant, while also aligning lessons with the digital skills required in modern education and the labour market.

5.3 TEACHER TRAINING AND RESOURCES

Even when curricula and pedagogical approaches are updated, the success of geoscience education ultimately depends on teachers. Surveys conducted across Europe indicate that most Earth science content in secondary schools is delivered by non-specialist teachers, who typically have backgrounds in geography, biology, or general science. This lack of dedicated training limits their confidence in teaching complex geological processes and discourages the use of innovative methods such as inquiry-based learning, fieldwork, or digital simulations.

To address this gap, targeted teacher training modules should be developed that focus on geothermal energy, critical raw materials, and their broader role in sustainability and the energy transition. These modules could be delivered as online courses, blended learning programmes, or workshops in collaboration with universities, professional associations, and national geological societies. Initiatives like the ENGIE project have already demonstrated the value of equipping teachers with thematic and methodological skills, which could be adapted and extended under CRM-geothermal's legacy.

Alongside training, teachers need access to high-quality educational resources. Ready-to-use lesson plans, infographics, case studies, and videos can help integrate geoscience topics into everyday teaching. The CRM-geothermal video contest has already produced engaging materials created by students for students, which can be incorporated into classrooms as discussion starters or project prompts. In addition, the "Educational material for teachers" repository initiated under Deliverable D6.4 will be expanded within this Educational Plan, ensuring that resources are freely available in multiple languages.

By investing in teacher capacity and resource development, schools can overcome one of the most persistent barriers to geoscience education. Well-trained and well-equipped teachers are not only more effective in communicating content but also more likely to inspire enthusiasm among students, thereby helping to build the next generation of geoscience-aware citizens and professionals.

5.4 STUDENT ENGAGEMENT AND AWARENESS-RAISING

Beyond curricular content and teacher support, motivating students to take an active interest in geoscience is essential. Evidence from the GEOschools and ENGIE surveys, as well as from the CRM-geothermal video contest, shows that students are most engaged when learning activities are interactive, creative, and connected to issues they consider relevant to their lives. Themes such as natural hazards, climate change, and sustainability consistently attract attention, while topics like raw materials and mining benefit from being framed in relation to technology, daily products, or climate action.

Schools can encourage engagement by organising contests, debates, and project-based activities. The CRM-geothermal video contest proved that creative formats enable students to act as science communicators, not just learners. Similar initiatives—such as poster competitions, school debates, or "science journalism" projects—could further enhance ownership of knowledge and peer-to-peer learning. Such activities should be designed to highlight the connection between geoscience and everyday issues, for example, linking geothermal energy to climate mitigation or illustrating how CRMs are essential for smartphones and renewable energy systems.

Digital platforms and social media can also play an important role in awareness-raising. While traditional outreach via school visits and textbooks remains valuable, today's students are digital natives. Youth-friendly channels such as TikTok, Instagram, or gamified learning environments can complement formal teaching, reaching students in the spaces where they already interact. In this way, geoscience communication can become more relatable, dynamic, and participatory.

Finally, student engagement should also include exposure to career opportunities. Many students remain unaware of the diverse pathways in geoscience, energy, and raw materials. Presenting real-life examples of professionals, internships, and higher education options can broaden students' horizons and help counter negative perceptions of the field. By combining creativity, interactivity, and career orientation, schools can ensure that geoscience is not only informative but also inspiring for the next generation.

5.5 PARTNERSHIPS AND NETWORKS

Schools cannot advance geoscience education in isolation. Effective teaching of topics such as geothermal energy and critical raw materials benefits from strong partnerships with external organisations that can provide expertise, resources, and opportunities for experiential learning. Establishing networks at local, national, and European levels is therefore a key recommendation of this Educational Plan.

At the local level, schools can collaborate with science museums, geoparks, natural history centres, and local universities to enrich classroom learning with hands-on experiences. Such institutions can host field trips, provide access to laboratories, or offer guest lectures that bring textbook concepts to life. Partnerships with local geothermal operators or raw material industries can also allow students to see how science translates into real-world applications, while simultaneously improving public awareness and acceptance of innovative technologies.

At the national and regional levels, professional associations, such as the European Federation of Geologists (EFG) and its affiliated national societies, can play a bridging role between schools and the geoscience community. These organisations are well placed to supply open-access teaching resources, organise teacher training workshops, and promote national competitions or events that highlight the societal relevance of geoscience.

At the European level, schools should connect with wider initiatives and networks that promote educational innovation. The European Geoparks Network, the Earth Learning Idea platform, and EU-funded projects such as ENGIE have already demonstrated how cross-border collaboration can scale up impact and inspire good practices. Integrating CRM-geothermal materials and approaches into such frameworks will extend the project's reach far beyond its immediate consortium.

By embedding geoscience education within a web of partnerships and networks, schools can access expertise and resources that would otherwise remain out of reach. At the same time, these partnerships help ensure that students, teachers, and communities remain connected to Europe's broader transition agenda, linking local classrooms with the global challenges of sustainability, raw material supply, and climate resilience.

5.6 SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

This chapter has outlined a series of recommendations for strengthening geoscience education in European secondary schools, with a particular emphasis on geothermal energy and critical raw materials. Building on the findings of international surveys, the lessons from the CRM-geothermal video contest, and examples of best practice across Europe, the recommendations address four interlinked dimensions: curricular integration, pedagogical innovation, teacher training, student engagement, and partnerships and networks (*Figure 7*).

The analysis shows that while Earth sciences remain underrepresented in curricula, there is significant potential to raise their profile by embedding them into broader themes of sustainability, energy transition, and climate change. Innovative teaching approaches, including inquiry-based learning,

fieldwork, virtual field trips, and gamified tools, can make these topics more accessible and appealing to students. Equally, investment in teacher training and resources is essential to overcome the current limitations of non-specialist teaching. Finally, sustained collaboration between schools and external actors such as universities, professional associations, museums, and industry can provide real-world contexts and ensure that education is closely connected to the skills needs of society.

Figure 7: Schematic framework summarising the five recommendation areas for secondary schools:

For the CRM-geothermal project, these recommendations directly support the exploitation strategy by building awareness of sustainable raw material supply and renewable energy at an early age, fostering societal acceptance, and inspiring the next generation of geoscientists and engineers. Looking ahead, the proposed measures can serve as a foundation for long-term improvements in secondary education, ensuring that Europe’s students are equipped with the knowledge, skills, and motivation to contribute to the twin green and digital transitions.

6 UNIVERSITY EDUCATION RELATED TO RAW MATERIALS AND GEOTHERMAL ENERGY

Higher education institutions play a decisive role in shaping the next generation of scientists, engineers, and decision-makers who will address Europe’s challenges in energy, climate, and raw material supply. From the aspects of the CRM-geothermal project, universities are particularly important because they provide the advanced skills and interdisciplinary knowledge required to design, operate, and govern innovative solutions for the co-production of geothermal energy and critical raw materials (CRMs). Ensuring that university programmes reflect these emerging needs is therefore essential for the long-term exploitation of project results.

At present, Europe faces a dual challenge. On the one hand, the European Green Deal and the EU Critical Raw Materials Act call for secure and sustainable access to CRMs, while also accelerating the shift to renewable energy sources. On the other hand, the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the EU Skills Agenda⁴ underline the urgency of equipping young professionals with the competences necessary to deliver this transition in a socially responsible and environmentally sustainable way. Bridging these policy priorities with academic education requires curricula that not

⁴ https://employment-social-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies-and-activities/skills-and-qualifications/european-skills-agenda_en

only strengthen technical geoscience knowledge but also integrate sustainability principles, digital competencies, and socio-economic perspectives.

Universities in Europe already offer a wide range of programmes in geology, mining engineering, raw materials, and geothermal energy. However, most of these are still designed around traditional disciplinary boundaries, with limited integration of the novel concept of geothermal–CRM co-production. By mapping current programmes, identifying gaps, and proposing targeted recommendations, this chapter seeks to provide a roadmap for aligning higher education with the strategic objectives of CRM-geothermal. In doing so, it aims to ensure that universities can serve as key multipliers of the project’s legacy, preparing graduates who are able to combine scientific excellence with sustainability and innovation for Europe’s future.

6.1 RAW-MATERIALS HIGHER EDUCATION IN EUROPE

European universities deliver a broad and mature portfolio of programmes along the raw-materials value chain, ranging from geology and mineral exploration to mining engineering, mineral processing, metallurgy, recycling and circular-economy specialisations. Mapping exercises undertaken over the past decade highlight both the breadth of the offer and persistent fragmentation across disciplines, learning outcomes and geographic regions. In *Annex 1*, a comprehensive list of European universities with raw material teaching content is provided.

6.1.1 Overview of the landscape

The INTERMIN H2020 project⁵ produced the most systematic overview to date, surveying programmes, defining skills lists and proposing joint international curricula. INTERMIN found high variability in programme depth and learning outcomes and recommended harmonised competence frameworks and mobility schemes to reduce skills mismatches across the value chain. It also proposed blueprints for joint training programmes to bridge institutional silos and regional gaps.

An earlier COBALT (FP7)⁶ work package on skills corroborated these findings: Europe faces structural skill shortages in parts of the minerals sector and needs targeted university syllabi, short courses and industry-linked training to respond to technological, environmental and societal demands. COBALT delivered draft university syllabi and a final report on skill-shortage mitigation, emphasising that improving general public knowledge about raw materials is also necessary to address social acceptance.

Over the same period, EIT RawMaterials has acted as a major integration mechanism, creating a pan-European RawMaterials Academy with a portfolio of EIT-labelled Master Schools (e.g., EMerald Georesources Engineering; AMIR recycling; SUMA sustainable materials; SINReM sustainable and innovative natural resource management). These programmes combine challenge-based pedagogy, multi-country mobility and entrepreneurship training, and are explicitly designed to align graduate skills with industry needs across exploration, extraction, processing, recycling and substitution⁷.

Professional bodies have converged on similar priorities. The Society of Mining Professors (SOMP) highlights the transformation of “mines of the future”, automation, data-driven operations, sustainability and novel mining systems, and calls for curricula that integrate digital competencies,

⁵ <https://interminproject.org>

⁶ <https://www.cobalt-fp7.eu>

⁷ <https://masters.eitrawmaterials.eu>

environmental and social performance, and systems thinking⁸. A selection of raw materials related university programmes in Europe are listed in *Table 5*.

Table 5: Selected European university programmes related to raw materials

Country	University / Programme	Focus Areas	Relevance for CRM-geothermal
Austria	Montanuniversität Leoben (Mining, Geoscience, Metallurgy)	Mining engineering, mineral processing, metallurgy, resource management	Strong raw materials focus; could integrate geothermal-CRM co-production concepts.
Germany	TU Bergakademie Freiberg (Faculty of Geosciences, Geoengineering and Mining)	Mining, geology, geoengineering, circular economy	Leading European school of mining; strong research in resource efficiency and recycling.
Germany	RWTH Aachen University (Faculty of Georesources and Materials Engineering)	Mining, georesources, materials engineering, geothermal research groups	Wide resource engineering base; excellent candidate for integrating CRM-geothermal modules.
Portugal	University of Porto (Faculty of Engineering)	Engineering geology, hydrogeology, resource management	Combines engineering and applied geology; scope for geothermal/CRM pilot integration.
Portugal	Instituto Superior Técnico, Lisboa	Geoscience, mining technology, environmental engineering	Offers multidisciplinary resource programmes; strong potential to embed sustainability/CRM focus.
Spain	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	Mining engineering, energy, applied geoscience	Bridges mining and energy; natural fit for geothermal-CRM co-production training.
UK	University of Exeter (Camborne School of Mines)	Mining engineering, geology, sustainable mining, raw materials MScs	Active in raw materials MSc consortia; strong EU connections; geothermal component could be added.
France	École Nationale Supérieure de Géologie, Nancy	Geology, mining, resource engineering	High-level geoscience programmes; alignment with EU raw materials strategy.
EU-wide	EIT RawMaterials Master Schools (e.g. EMerald, SUMA, AMIR)	Sustainable raw materials, circular economy, materials innovation	Pan-European network of joint MScs; platform to insert CRM-geothermal content.

6.1.2 Gaps and challenges

A thematic trend across European universities is the progressive integration of sustainability and circular-economy content into core mining/georesources curricula. Case-based analyses of curriculum reform demonstrate how sustainability principles can be embedded through lifecycle perspectives, stakeholder engagement and environmental stewardship, rather than treating them as add-on modules (Binder et al. 2018). This aligns with EU policy drivers – most notably the Critical Raw Materials Act (CRMA) – which sets explicit targets for secure and sustainable supply and implicitly raises the bar for workforce competencies in permitting, ESG, recycling and strategic value-chain development. Despite these advances, several gaps persist. Fragmentation and uneven coverage remains an issue. INTERMIN’s mapping shows that while exploration, mining and processing are well represented,

⁸ <https://miningprofs.org>

programmes that span the full value chain – including design for recycling, urban mining, substitution and advanced materials – are still comparatively rare outside the EIT-labelled network. Joint curricula and recognition frameworks remain the exception rather than the rule.

Skills mismatch and harmonisation needs require further effort and investigation. Both COBALT and INTERMIN document mismatches between graduate competencies and evolving industrial needs (automation, data analytics, environmental assessment, stakeholder engagement). They recommend harmonised learning outcomes and modular, stackable training that can be shared across institutions. Insufficient interdisciplinary depth has significant impact. Academic offerings often remain siloed (e.g., strong geology with limited processing/recycling, or vice versa). Peer-reviewed work compiling a comprehensive skills catalogue for the raw-materials sector argues for broader competence profiles that couple domain knowledge with digital skills, systems engineering and sustainability (Hartlieb et al. 2020)

Digital transformation and innovation skills still are underdeveloped. SOMP's and sector analyses stress the need for stronger training in automation, sensing, AI/ML, geometallurgy data pipelines and integrated decision-support. Entrepreneurship and innovation management – widely used in EIT programmes, are less consistently embedded elsewhere.

Societal interface and governance need further integration. With the CRMA accelerating domestic projects, universities must reinforce training in permitting, impact assessment, community engagement and responsible supply chains (ESG). Current provision is uneven, and often addressed through electives rather than core learning outcomes.

6.1.3 Policy context and institutional drivers

The Critical Raw Materials Act (2024) strengthens the urgency of addressing the listed gaps by setting clear targets for domestic sourcing and processing capacity. This policy shift implies a direct need for university programmes to embed ESG competences, permitting and governance knowledge, and cross-disciplinary training.

At the institutional level, Europe hosts several long-standing centres of excellence, such as Montanuniversität Leoben (Austria), RWTH Aachen and TU Bergakademie Freiberg (Germany), and UK/Portuguese schools (e.g., University of Exeter's Camborne School of Mines; University of Porto/IST Lisboa), that cover key segments of the value chain and increasingly engage with sustainability and circularity themes, often within EIT RawMaterials networks or other EU projects. These institutions are well-positioned to spearhead joint degrees and micro-credential pathways that reflect the skills frameworks emerging from INTERMIN/COBALT and the policy direction set by the CRMA.

6.1.4 Implications for CRM-geothermal

For a project aiming to co-production concepts (energy + raw materials) and responsible sourcing, Europe's raw-materials education provides a strong base but requires targeted curriculum integration to:

- Connect subsurface characterisation, extraction and processing with recycling and responsible supply-chain management,
- Embed ESG and permitting competences as core objectives, and
- Develop data-centric and automation skills.

EIT-labelled Master Schools offer ready-made models for mobility, industry projects, and entrepreneurship. INTERMIN's competence frameworks and joint-programme blueprints can guide harmonisation and mutual recognition. COBALT's syllabi provide content starting points for sustainability and societal modules. A schematic diagram showing the flow from strengths through gaps and needed reforms to implications for CRM-geothermal is shown in *Figure 8*.

Figure 8: From current strengths to CRM-geothermal implications in raw materials higher education

As a summary, European raw-materials higher education is moving in the right direction, more networked, more sustainability-oriented and increasingly entrepreneurial, yet still heterogeneous in coverage and depth. To meet the CRMA’s strategic ambitions and the skills required by emerging co-production approaches, universities should

- expand value-chain-spanning curricula,
- modularise and jointly accredit programmes across borders,
- promote ESG and stakeholder engagement training, and
- accelerate digital competencies and innovation skills across geology, mining and processing.

Doing so would tighten the link between EU policy objectives and graduate capabilities, and directly support the exploitation and legacy goals of CRM-geothermal.

6.2 GEOTHERMAL HIGHER EDUCATION IN EUROPE

Geothermal higher education in Europe plays a crucial role in training the specialists required for the energy transition. Universities provide the scientific, engineering, and policy competencies necessary to explore, design, and operate geothermal systems; yet, the educational landscape remains fragmented and uneven in scope. While some institutions offer fully dedicated master’s programmes in geothermal engineering or geology, most universities cover geothermal topics only as elective modules within broader geoscience, hydrogeology, or energy curricula. This situation reflects both the interdisciplinary nature of geothermal energy, which spans geology, engineering, environmental sciences, and economics, and the historical dominance of fossil–fuel–oriented subsurface education. In recent years, EU policy frameworks such as the European Green Deal, the EU Critical Raw Materials Act, and the EU Skills Agenda have sharpened the need for specialised geothermal training, not only as a renewable energy technology but also as a potential co-production pathway for critical raw materials.

6.2.1 Overview of the landscape

Geothermal education in Europe has developed steadily since the 1970s, but remains highly heterogeneous across countries and institutions. The GeoElec project (2014) identified more than 30 universities offering geothermal exploration or engineering modules, although only a small fraction provided dedicated master’s programmes (Spalek et al. 2014). Most geothermal education is

embedded within the curricula of Earth sciences, hydrogeology, petroleum engineering, or energy engineering, highlighting its interdisciplinary character.

Dedicated programmes exist at institutions such as FAU Erlangen–Nürnberg and TUM (Germany), Montanuniversität Leoben (Austria), University of Neuchâtel (Switzerland), and the University of Edinburgh (UK). In France, the University of Strasbourg (GeoT) and the University of Pau run geothermal courses and field schools, while in Italy, universities such as the University of Pisa and Roma Tre offer specialisations within geoscience programmes. Non-EU actors such as Reykjavik University (Iceland) continue to play an influential role, with long-standing links to European capacity building through the UN Geothermal Training Programme (*Table 6*).

Table 6: Selected European university programmes related to geothermal energy

Country	University / Faculty	Programme / Specialisation	Notes / Source
Austria	Montanuniversität Leoben	Geoenergy Engineering (M.Sc)	https://www.unileoben.ac.at/en/studying/graduate-studies/resources/geoenergy-engineering
France	University of Strasbourg (GeoT)	Geothermal exploration / energy modules	Course+field school in geothermal energy (https://geot.unistra.fr/educationgeot.unistra.fr)
France	University of Pau / Pays de l'Adour	SAGE – Sustainable Geoennergies	Master combining geoscience, energy & environment.
Germany	FAU Erlangen-Nürnberg & TUM	Geothermal Energy (M.Sc.) (joint)	Covers exploration, reservoir modelling, utilization. (https://www.nat.fau.eu)
Germany	TUM / FAU	GeoThermics / GeoEnergy (M.Sc.)	Emphasis on geothermal systems and subsurface energy (https://www.ed.tum.de)
Germany	TU Clausthal	Geothermal Engineering (M.Sc.)	Program has been advertised (status to verify)
Germany	TU Bergakademie Freiberg	Proposed geothermal / geoenergy programme	Strong mining & resource research base; geothermal program in planning or development
Germany	TH Georg Agricola (Bochum)	Geoengineering / Post-Mining (M.Eng)	While not purely geothermal, it involves subsurface/engineering topics.
Iceland	Reykjavik University / Iceland School of Energy	MSc in Sustainable Energy with geothermal emphasis	Though non-EU, relevant for completeness (historical geothermal education in EU contexts).
Italy	University of Pisa	Geothermal specialization (module)	Specialization in geothermal resource exploration (http://www.geoelec.eu)
Italy	University Roma3	Geothermal module / specialization	http://www.geoelec.eu
Switzerland	University of Neuchâtel / CHYN	Hydrogeology & Geothermics (M.Sc.)	Focus on groundwater and geothermal coupling.
United Kingdom	University of Edinburgh, School of GeoSciences	MSc GeoEnergy	Combines energy topics, geological and system perspectives (https://edadfed.ed.ac.uk)
Europe (pan-regional / professional)	IEP (Institute of Environmental Professions)	Geothermics & Geothermal Applications (M.Sc)	Operational qualification in geothermal exploitation (https://iep.edu.eu/cgi-sy)
4 countries	Geo3En partner universities	Proposed Erasmus Mundus Master in Geothermal Engineering	Network initiative to build shared geothermal education across Europe (https://geo3en.eu/)

6.2.2 Strengths of Current Programmes

European universities are recognised worldwide for their expertise in reservoir characterisation, hydrogeology, and geoscience modelling. Flagship programmes such as CHYN's Hydrogeology and Geothermics MSc in Neuchâtel⁹ and the GeoT programme in Strasbourg¹⁰ exemplify advanced integration of geoscience and field-based education.

Another strength lies in applied and experiential learning. Programmes often include fieldwork, laboratory sessions, and real-data modelling, ensuring that graduates gain practical experience. For example, Strasbourg's field school requires students to construct geothermal reservoir models, while Montanuniversität Leoben links geoenery teaching with industrial pilot projects.

Collaboration initiatives such as the proposed Geo3En¹¹ network demonstrate momentum towards joint, harmonised curricula at the European level, similar to what EIT RawMaterials has achieved in raw materials education.

6.2.3 Integration of Sustainability and Policy Context

Geothermal education is increasingly aligned with sustainability narratives, positioning geothermal as a low-carbon energy source supporting the European Green Deal and the EU Skills Agenda. Environmental aspects, resource efficiency, and climate mitigation are common components of curricula.

However, integration remains partial. ESG (environmental, social, and governance) competences and socio-economic aspects of geothermal development, such as permitting, stakeholder engagement, and public acceptance, are usually taught as electives or project options, not as compulsory core elements. This contrasts with the growing policy emphasis on social licence to operate and community benefits.

6.2.4 Gaps and challenges

Despite progress, several challenges and limitations persist in geothermal higher education:

- Limited dedicated programmes, only a handful of universities offer fully dedicated geothermal degrees; most treat geothermal as an elective.
- Fragmentation of focus, some programmes emphasise geoscience (hydrogeology, reservoir geology), while others focus on engineering (drilling, plant design), with insufficient integration across the full value chain.
- Absence of standard frameworks, unlike raw materials (INTERMIN), geothermal education lacks a harmonised competence framework, making it difficult to compare programmes across countries.
- Digitalisation gap, few curricula systematically integrate big data, AI, or advanced reservoir modelling, though these are increasingly critical in exploration and monitoring.
- Weak linkage to raw materials, the concept of co-production of CRMs from geothermal fluids, central to CRM-geothermal, is almost absent in existing courses.

⁹ <https://www.unine.ch/chyn>

¹⁰ <https://geot.unistra.fr/>

¹¹ <https://geo3en.eu/>

6.2.5 Implications for CRM-geothermal

For CRM-geothermal, the current landscape offers a strong scientific and engineering foundation, but requires targeted updates to align with future needs:

- Introduce co-production concepts, linking geothermal utilisation with CRM recovery.
- Expand interdisciplinarity, bridging geoscience, engineering, economics, and social sciences.
- Mainstream ESG competences, making environmental and stakeholder modules compulsory rather than elective.
- Accelerate digitalisation training, including AI-based reservoir modelling and real-time monitoring.
- Foster European collaboration, leveraging networks such as Geo3En to create joint degrees and mobility schemes.

By addressing these challenges, geothermal higher education can prepare graduates to lead innovation in co-production and sustainable energy systems, directly contributing to the exploitation and long-term legacy of the CRM-geothermal project. The flow from strengths to CRM-geothermal implications is shown in *Figure 9*.

Figure 9: From current strengths to CRM-geothermal implications in geothermal higher education

7 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR UNIVERSITIES

Universities are central to the long-term success and exploitation of the CRM-geothermal project. They are the primary institutions responsible for training the geoscientists, engineers, and policy experts who will implement Europe’s twin transition towards climate neutrality and digitalisation. Higher education therefore, provides the key link between project-level research and the skilled workforce required to scale up geothermal–CRM co-production technologies across Europe.

The assessment presented in Chapter 6 shows that European higher education already has a strong foundation, with internationally recognised expertise in geology, mining engineering, and geothermal science. Centres of excellence such as Montanuniversität Leoben, RWTH Aachen, TU Bergakademie Freiberg, the University of Porto, the University of Exeter, and specialised geothermal programmes at FAU Erlangen–Nürnberg, TUM, Strasbourg, Neuchâtel, and Edinburgh demonstrate the breadth of

capacity that exists. At the same time, significant gaps remain: curricula are fragmented, few universities offer dedicated geothermal programmes, and there is limited integration of sustainability, ESG competences, digitalisation, and most critically the co-production of critical raw materials from geothermal fluids.

Addressing these gaps is not only an academic challenge but also a strategic necessity. European policy frameworks such as the European Green Deal, the Critical Raw Materials Act, the EU Skills Agenda, and the Sustainable Development Goals explicitly call for secure, sustainable supplies of energy and raw materials, supported by a well-trained workforce. Universities must therefore adapt their curricula to reflect these priorities, ensuring that graduates are equipped with interdisciplinary competences that cover the entire value chain, from subsurface exploration and resource characterisation to processing, recycling, environmental governance, and stakeholder engagement.

Figure 10: Framework for the recommendations for universities

The recommendations described in the following sections translate the findings of Chapter 6 into concrete, actionable proposals for higher education institutions. They cover curriculum integration and modernisation, the development of new modules and interdisciplinary programmes, expansion of experiential learning, and alignment with EU policy frameworks (Figure 10). Together, they provide a roadmap for embedding CRM-geothermal knowledge into European higher education, thereby securing the project’s legacy and contributing directly to Europe’s strategic autonomy in energy and raw materials.

The recommendations, related key actions, and expected impact are summarised in Table 7.

Table 7: Summary of recommendations for universities for embedding the CRM-geothermal knowledge into the higher education

Area	Recommendation	Key Actions	Expected Impact
Curriculum Integration & Modernisation	Embed geothermal–CRM co-production into geology, mining, and energy curricula	Revise syllabi; align with competence frameworks (INTERMIN, Geo3En); add systems-thinking perspectives	Graduates able to understand synergies between renewable energy and raw materials
New Modules and Courses	Introduce modules on geothermal fluids as CRM sources, ESG/geoethics, digitalisation, and circular economy	Design elective courses first; progressively expand into core curricula; use CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas as teaching tool	Broader competence profiles; technical, digital, and societal skills embedded
Interdisciplinary Programmes & Joint Degrees	Develop Erasmus Mundus-style MScs combining geoscience, engineering, policy, and sustainability	Pool expertise across universities (e.g. Leoben, Aachen, Freiberg, Porto, Exeter, Strasbourg); create mobility pathways	Joint degrees with unique competence profiles; harmonisation of European higher education
Experiential & Applied Learning	Strengthen fieldwork, internships, and digital/virtual training	Use demonstrator sites, Fluid Atlas datasets, VR/AR, and industry-linked theses	Hands-on competences; improved employability and innovation readiness
Alignment with EU Policy Priorities	Integrate CRMA, Green Deal, SDGs, and EU Skills Agenda into education	Develop policy case studies; involve regulators in teaching; simulate permitting and stakeholder processes	Graduates prepared to operate in policy and governance contexts; better social licence outcomes

7.1 CURRICULUM INTEGRATION AND MODERNISATION

A first and fundamental recommendation is to strengthen the integration of geothermal energy and critical raw materials (CRM) co-production into existing university curricula. At present, most European programmes in geology, mining, or energy engineering treat geothermal energy and raw materials as separate domains, if they address them at all. This fragmentation limits students' understanding of the synergies between renewable energy production and sustainable resource supply.

Curriculum modernisation should therefore ensure that geothermal–CRM co-production concepts are embedded as cross-cutting themes within geoscience and engineering degrees. For example, geothermal modules could explicitly address the recovery of lithium or rare earth elements from geothermal fluids, thereby linking reservoir geology and hydrogeochemistry with mineral processing and circular economy strategies. Similarly, mining and raw-materials programmes should broaden their perspective to include subsurface energy as a resource dimension alongside conventional extraction.

The integration process can build on existing competence frameworks such as those developed by the INTERMIN project for raw materials education and by emerging geothermal education networks (e.g. Geo3En). Universities should align learning outcomes with these frameworks, ensuring comparability and mobility of graduates across Europe. In doing so, institutions will not only enhance the coherence of curricula but also create pathways for joint accreditation and Erasmus-type exchanges, reinforcing the European Higher Education Area.

Modernisation should also include the incorporation of systems thinking. Students must be educated to understand resource development as a complex socio-technical system that combines geological, technical, environmental, and societal dimensions. Embedding such integrative perspectives in curricula will better prepare graduates to work in interdisciplinary teams and to respond to the multifaceted challenges of the energy and raw materials transition.

By explicitly integrating CRM-geothermal concepts and updating curricula accordingly, universities will ensure that future professionals are equipped to implement innovative solutions that contribute simultaneously to Europe’s energy security, raw material supply, and climate-neutrality objectives.

7.2 DEVELOPMENT OF NEW MODULES AND COURSES

While curriculum integration provides the structural framework, universities also need to design and implement new modules and courses that address emerging knowledge areas at the intersection of geothermal energy and critical raw materials. These modules should go beyond traditional geology, mining, and engineering training, introducing students to the scientific, technological, and societal dimensions of co-production.

Figure 11: Thematic priorities for new modules and courses

Four main thematic priorities can be identified (Figure 11):

- Sustainable raw materials from geothermal fluids, courses should explore the geochemistry of geothermal brines, mineral recovery technologies, and the potential for lithium, rare earths, and other CRMs to be sourced sustainably from geothermal reservoirs. Linking geoscience with mineral processing and environmental engineering will equip students with knowledge directly relevant to CRM-geothermal.
- Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) and geoethics, new teaching units should address the broader context of geothermal and raw-materials projects, including environmental impact assessment, social licence to operate, community engagement, and ethical responsibility in resource development. Embedding ESG competences into university curricula will prepare graduates for the governance challenges associated with Europe’s energy transition.
- Digitalisation and advanced modelling, geothermal and raw-materials exploration increasingly rely on digital tools such as big data analytics, machine learning, and real-time monitoring. New courses should introduce students to these technologies, focusing on their application in reservoir modelling, exploration targeting, and process optimisation.
- Circular economy and value-chain integration, modules should highlight how geothermal–CRM co-production contributes to circular resource use, reducing waste, and maximising value across the resource and energy system. This aligns with broader EU strategies for sustainable materials management.

These new courses can be introduced as electives in the short term and progressively expanded into core components of geology, mining, and energy programmes. They can also form the basis for new joint or Erasmus Mundus master's programmes, ensuring visibility and mobility across European universities.

By developing such modules, universities will ensure that their graduates are not only technically competent but also socially and environmentally literate, digitally skilled, and capable of contributing to Europe's leadership in sustainable geothermal-CRM co-production.

7.3 INTERDISCIPLINARY PROGRAMMES AND JOINT DEGREES

Geothermal-CRM co-production is by definition an interdisciplinary endeavour, spanning geology, hydrogeology, geochemistry, mining engineering, reservoir engineering, materials science, process engineering, environmental studies, economics, and policy. Preparing graduates to work effectively in this space requires educational formats that break down disciplinary silos and foster collaboration across faculties and institutions.

A key recommendation is the development of interdisciplinary master's programmes and joint degrees. These should integrate the technical foundations of geoscience and engineering with educating in sustainability, economics, and governance. Such programmes could follow the successful models already implemented in the raw-materials sector, notably the EIT RawMaterials-labelled Master Schools (e.g. EMerald, SUMA, AMIR, SINReM), which combine multi-country mobility, entrepreneurship training, and industry-linked projects.

In geothermal education, promising initiatives are already emerging. The proposed Geo3En network aims to establish a joint Erasmus Mundus Master in Geothermal Engineering, uniting institutions across Europe under a common curriculum. This approach can serve as a blueprint for CRM-geothermal, ensuring that students benefit from mobility, harmonised learning outcomes, and exposure to diverse geological and technological settings.

Joint degrees also enable resource sharing and efficiency. Universities with strengths in different domains (e.g. Montanuniversität Leoben in mining, FAU/TUM in geothermal, RWTH Aachen in georesources, and Porto/Exeter in resource engineering) can pool expertise to deliver comprehensive programmes. This integration will create graduates with unique competence profiles, combining technical excellence with cross-disciplinary systems understanding.

To be effective, such programmes should also embed industry and policy perspectives. Partnerships with geothermal operators, raw-materials companies, and regulatory agencies can ensure that case studies, internships, and thesis projects address real-world challenges. This will strengthen employability while reinforcing the strategic relevance of academic training.

By investing in interdisciplinary and joint master's programmes, European universities will ensure that the next generation of professionals is prepared to implement co-production concepts, bridging scientific innovation, industrial application, and policy frameworks in support of the CRM-geothermal exploitation strategy.

7.4 EXPERIENTIAL AND APPLIED LEARNING

Beyond classroom teaching, experiential and applied learning is essential for preparing students to work in geothermal-CRM co-production. The complexity of subsurface systems, the integration of energy and raw materials, and the need for societal acceptance all require graduates who can apply theoretical knowledge to real-world contexts.

Universities should therefore expand opportunities for fieldwork, laboratory practice, and industry collaboration. Traditional geoscience field courses remain valuable, but should increasingly be complemented by site visits to geothermal plants, pilot projects, and raw-material extraction facilities. These experiences allow students to see directly how geological, engineering, and environmental factors interact in practice.

Where direct site access is limited, universities can adopt virtual field trips and simulation-based training. Recent advances in VR/AR technologies and digital twins enable students to explore geothermal reservoirs, model mineral recovery processes, and engage in scenario-based decision making. Such tools not only improve accessibility but also support training in advanced digital competences.

Internships and thesis projects conducted in collaboration with industry, research institutes, and regulatory agencies should become a standard component of programmes. The CRM-geothermal demonstrator sites and the project's Fluid Atlas offer excellent resources for student projects, combining real datasets with cutting-edge methodologies. Involving students in these activities ensures a direct link between education and research, while also strengthening the exploitation of project outputs.

Finally, experiential learning should extend to societal and governance dimensions. Students can participate in role-play exercises or stakeholder simulations that reproduce the permitting, policy, and community engagement processes associated with geothermal–CRM projects. This exposure equips graduates with the soft skills required to navigate the socio-political environment of resource development.

By systematically embedding experiential and applied learning into curricula, universities can ensure that students graduate not only with strong technical foundations but also with the practical, digital, and socio-economic competences necessary to implement CRM-geothermal innovations.

7.5 ALIGNMENT WITH EU POLICY PRIORITIES

For university curricula to remain relevant and impactful, they must be aligned with the strategic policy frameworks that guide Europe's energy and raw-materials transition. The European Green Deal sets the overarching objective of climate neutrality by 2050, while the Critical Raw Materials Act (CRMA, 2023) establishes targets for domestic sourcing, processing, and recycling of strategic materials. Complementing these are the EU Skills Agenda, which emphasises training for the green and digital transitions, and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which set global benchmarks for responsible resource use and climate action.

Universities should therefore integrate policy-oriented content directly into their teaching. This can take the form of dedicated modules on resource governance and policy frameworks where students should gain familiarity with the CRMA, EU taxonomy regulations, and permitting processes for geothermal and mining projects.

Case studies and simulation exercises that can analyse real permitting cases, impact assessments, or stakeholder conflicts, allowing students to explore decision-making under regulatory constraints. Policy–science integration with joint teaching with legal scholars, policy experts, and regulators can help bridge disciplinary divides, giving students an understanding of how technical assessments translate into policy actions. International outlook based on supply chains and energy systems are global, curricula should also situate European policies within the context of international agreements, such as the Paris Agreement and the UN SDGs.

By embedding these elements, universities will ensure that their graduates are not only skilled scientists and engineers but also informed actors in the governance of raw materials and renewable energy. This will help bridge the gap between technological innovation and societal implementation, ensuring that CRM-geothermal approaches can be deployed effectively within Europe’s evolving regulatory and policy environment.

7.6 ROADMAP FOR IMPLEMENTATION

Transforming university curricula to integrate geothermal–CRM co-production requires a phased approach that balances immediate opportunities with long-term structural reforms. The following roadmap provides a framework for universities, policymakers, and industry partners to coordinate actions over different time horizons (*Figure 12*).

Figure 12: Roadmap for implementing CRM-geothermal recommendations in universities

Short-term (1–2 years)

- Introduce elective modules on geothermal–CRM topics within existing geology, mining, and energy programmes.
- Use CRM-geothermal outputs such as the Fluid Atlas and demonstrator datasets as teaching resources.
- Pilot interdisciplinary seminars bringing together geoscience, engineering, and sustainability students.
- Establish short training workshops on ESG, permitting, and stakeholder engagement.

Medium-term (3–5 years)

- Develop interdisciplinary joint MSc programmes (e.g. Erasmus Mundus style) combining raw materials and geothermal energy.
- Expand industry collaboration, including structured internships at geothermal plants, mining companies, and regulatory agencies.
- Integrate digitalisation tools (AI, machine learning, digital twins) into geoscience and engineering curricula.
- Create policy-oriented case-study courses aligned with the CRMA, Green Deal, and SDGs.

Long-term (5+ years)

- Institutionalise dedicated degree programmes in geothermal–CRM co-production, supported by European networks such as Geo3En and EIT RawMaterials.
- Establish harmonised competence frameworks for geothermal education, similar to INTERMIN’s blueprint for raw materials.

- Foster European centres of excellence through partnerships between leading universities (e.g. Leoben, RWTH Aachen, Freiberg, Porto, Exeter, Strasbourg).
- Secure long-term funding mechanisms for continuous curriculum modernisation and student mobility across Europe.

This roadmap highlights that some changes can be implemented quickly, through electives, teaching materials, and pilot workshops, while others require deeper institutional commitments and cross-European collaboration. By following these steps, universities will progressively align their programmes with Europe’s policy priorities and provide a resilient workforce capable of delivering CRM-geothermal innovations.

8 CONCLUSIONS

This Educational Plan has examined the current state of geosciences, raw materials, and geothermal education in Europe, with a particular focus on secondary schools and universities. It has identified both the strengths of existing provision and the persistent gaps that must be addressed in order to prepare the next generation of citizens, scientists, and engineers for the challenges of Europe's twin green and digital transition.

At the secondary school level, geoscience education is often underrepresented in curricula, typically integrated into broader subjects, such as geography or general science. Innovative pedagogical approaches, such as inquiry-based learning, fieldwork, virtual simulations, and socio-scientific debates, can substantially increase student engagement, especially when linked to topics of high societal relevance such as climate change, renewable energy, and critical raw materials. The CRM-geothermal video contest has demonstrated the potential of creative, participatory activities to raise awareness among young people. Recommendations therefore emphasise curricular integration, modern teaching approaches, enhanced teacher training, and stronger partnerships between schools, universities, museums, and industry.

At the university level, Europe benefits from strong centres of excellence in geology, mining, and geothermal science, but programmes remain fragmented and often siloed. Raw-materials education has advanced through initiatives such as the INTERMIN competence framework and the EIT RawMaterials-labelled Master Schools, while geothermal education is only beginning to develop joint curricula such as the proposed Geo3En network. Across both domains, key gaps include the integration of sustainability and ESG competences, digitalisation and automation skills, and most importantly the absence of modules on geothermal-CRM co-production. Recommendations therefore call for curriculum modernisation, the creation of new modules and interdisciplinary programmes, the strengthening of experiential learning, and the alignment of teaching with EU policy priorities, particularly the European Green Deal, the Critical Raw Materials Act, and the EU Skills Agenda.

Taken together, these recommendations provide a roadmap for embedding CRM-geothermal concepts into European education at all levels. They aim to ensure that students acquire not only technical knowledge but also the interdisciplinary, digital, and socio-political competences required to support sustainable energy and raw-materials development. In doing so, they directly contribute to the project's exploitation strategy by raising awareness, fostering societal acceptance, and creating a skilled workforce capable of implementing geothermal-CRM co-production in practice.

Looking forward, the successful implementation of this Educational Plan will help to foster a new generation of geoscientists and engineers. These professionals will be equipped not only with cutting-edge technical expertise but also with the ethical, digital, and policy competences needed to deliver on the EU's twin transition: the green shift to climate neutrality and the digital transformation of industry and society. By investing in education today, CRM-geothermal ensures that Europe can meet its strategic objectives for climate neutrality, resource security, and innovation, while leaving a lasting legacy for future generations.

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10 ANNEX 1: UNIVERSITIES IN EUROPE WITH RELEVANT GEOSCIENCE AND RAW MATERIAL TEACHING CONTENT

Source:

- EIT RawMaterials;
- COBALT project, Deliverable D3.1 - Education related to mineral raw materials in the European Union, 2014;
- INTERMIN project, Preliminary survey results, 2019;
- Society of Mining Professors: 2020 Report on Student and Faculty Numbers in Mining Engineering Programs.

Country	University	Department/Programme
Austria	Montanuniversität Leoben	Department of Mineral Resources and Petroleum Engineering
Austria	Graz University of Technology	Geoscience
Austria	University of Innsbruck	Geoscience
Belgium	KU Leuven	SUMA Master Programme on Sustainable Materials
Belgium	University of Mons	['Geoscience', 'Mining Technology']
Belgium	University of Liège	EMerald Master in Resources Engineering
Bulgaria	University of Mining and Geology St. Ivan Rilski	'Geoscience', 'Mining Technology']
Croatia	University of Zagreb	Faculty of Mining, Geology and Petroleum Engineering
Czech Republic	Charles University	Faculty of Science, Department of Geology
Czech Republic	Technical University of Ostrava	Faculty of Mining and Geology
Denmark	University of Copenhagen	Department of Geosciences and Natural Resource Management
Estonia	University of Tartu	Department of Geology
Estonia	Tallinn University of Technology	['Geoscience', 'Mining Technology', 'Environmental Engineering']
Finland	Aalto University	School of Chemical Engineering
Finland	Abo Akademi University	['Geoscience', 'Metallurgy']
Finland	University of Helsinki	Department of Geosciences and Geography
Finland	University of Oulu	Oulu Mining School
Finland	Kajaani University of Applied Sciences	['Geoscience', 'Mining Technology']
Finland	Lappia University of Applied Sciences	['Geoscience', 'Mining Technology']
France	University of Lorraine	EMerald Master in Resources Engineering
France	École Nationale Supérieure de Géologie	Department of Geology
France	MINES ParisTech	['Geoscience', 'Environmental Engineering']
France	Ecole des Mines de Douai	['Metallurgy', 'Environmental Engineering']
France	Ecole des Mines de Nancy	['Geoscience', 'Mining Technology', 'Environmental Engineering', 'Recycling']
Germany	Clausthal University of Technology	Institute of Mining

Germany	RWTH Aachen University	Faculty of Georesources and Materials Engineering
Germany	Technische Hochschule Georg Agricola	Geo-Resources and Process Engineering
Germany	TU Bergakademie Freiberg	Faculty of Geosciences, Geoengineering and Mining
Germany	Technische Universität Berlin	['Geoscience']
Germany	Technische Universität Clausthal	['Geoscience', 'Mineral Processing', 'Metallurgy', 'Environmental Engineering']
Germany	University of Hannover	['Geoscience']
Germany	TFH Georg Agricola	['Geoscience', 'Mining Technology']
Greece	National Technical University of Athens	School of Mining and Metallurgical Engineering
Greece	Technical University of Crete	School of Mineral Resources Engineering
Greece	University of Western Macedonia	Department of Mineral Resources Engineering
Hungary	University of Miskolc	Faculty of Earth Science and Engineering
Hungary	University of Szeged	Department of Mineralogy, Geochemistry and Petrology
Ireland	University of Limerick	['Geoscience', 'Environmental Engineering']
Ireland	Trinity College Dublin	['Geoscience', 'Environmental Engineering']
Ireland	University College Cork	['Geoscience', 'Environmental Engineering']
Ireland	University College Dublin	['Geoscience', 'Environmental Engineering']
Iceland	University of Iceland	Faculty of Earth Sciences
Italy	University of Cagliari	['Geoscience', 'Metallurgy']
Italy	University of Trieste	['Geoscience']
Italy	University of Bologna	['Geoscience']
Italy	Politecnico di Milano-Bicocca	SUMA Master Programme on Sustainable Materials
Italy	University of Trento	SUMA Master Programme on Sustainable Materials
Latvia	University of Latvia	Department of Geology
Lithuania	Vilnius University	Department of Geology and Mineralogy
Netherlands	Delft University of Technology	Department of Geoscience and Engineering
Norway	University of Bergen	Department of Earth Science
Norway	University of Oslo	Department of Geosciences
Poland	AGH University of Science and Technology	Faculty of Mining and Geoengineering
Poland	University of Warsaw	Faculty of Geology
Poland	University of Wrocław	Institute of Geological Sciences
Poland	Czestochowa University of Technology	['Metallurgy']
Poland	Lodz University of Technology	['Environmental Engineering']
Poland	Poznan University of Technology	['Recycling']
Poland	Silesian University of Technology	['Geoscience', 'Mining Technology', 'Metallurgy', 'Environmental Engineering']

Poland	Wroclaw University of Technology	['Geoscience', 'Mining Technology', 'Environmental Engineering']
Portugal	University of Porto	Faculty of Engineering
Portugal	Instituto Superior Tecnico, Lisboa	['Geoscience', 'Mining Technology']
Portugal	University of Evora	Geoscience
Romania	University of Bucharest	Faculty of Geology and Geophysics
Romania	Technical University of Petrosani	['Mining Technology', 'Environmental Engineering']
Romania	Technical University of Cluj-Napoca	['Mining Technology', 'Mineral Processing', 'Environmental Engineering']
Serbia	University of Belgrade	Faculty of Mining and Geology
Slovakia	Comenius University	Faculty of Natural Sciences, Geology and Paleontology
Slovenia	University of Ljubljana	Faculty of Natural Sciences and Engineering
Spain	Universidad de Vigo	Higher School of Mining Engineering
Spain	Universidad Politécnic de Madrid	School of Mining and Energy Engineering
Spain	Universidad de Oviedo	['Geoscience', 'Mining Technology', 'Environmental Engineering']
Spain	Universitat Politecnica de Catalunya	['Geoscience', 'Metallurgy']
Spain	Escuela Politécnic Superior de Linares	Department of Mining Engineering
Sweden	Luleå University of Technology	Department of Civil, Environmental and Natural Resources Eng.
Sweden	University of Gothenburg	Department of Earth Sciences
Sweden	Uppsala University	Department of Earth Sciences
Sweden	Chalmers University of Technology	['Geoscience', 'Environmental Engineering']
Sweden	KTH Royal Institute of Technology	['Geoscience', 'Metallurgy']
Sweden	Lund University	['Geoscience', 'Metallurgy']
Sweden	Stockholm University	['Geoscience']
United Kingdom	University of Aberdeen	School of Geosciences
United Kingdom	University of Dundee	Centre for Energy, Petroleum and Mineral Law and Policy (CEPMLP)
United Kingdom	University of Edinburgh	School of GeoSciences
United Kingdom	University of Exeter	Camborne School of Mines
United Kingdom	University of St Andrews	Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences
United Kingdom	Cardiff University	['Geoscience']
United Kingdom	Imperial College London	['Geoscience', 'Mining Technology', 'Metallurgy']
United Kingdom	University of Leeds	['Geoscience', 'Metallurgy']
United Kingdom	University of Manchester	['Geoscience', 'Metallurgy']
United Kingdom	University of Sheffield	['Metallurgy', 'Environmental Engineering']
United Kingdom	University of Glasgow	Geoscience